

RESPONSE OF AS4/PEEK COMPOSITE LATTICE STRUCTURES UNDER THE COMPRESSION AND LOW VELOCITY IMPACT LOADING

Jiqiang Hu¹, Bing Wang^{1*}, Yijie Zhao¹

¹ Center for Composite Materials and Structures, Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin, China

Email: wangbing86@hit.edu.cn

Introduction

Lightweight sandwich structures with advanced processing techniques are essential for the future industrial development [1]. Previous studies on sandwich structures mainly focused on metal materials or thermosetting composites, but there are few studies on sandwich structures of thermoplastic composites, especially advanced thermoplastic composites. Advanced thermoplastic composites offer many advantages over conventional thermosetting composites such as epoxy-based composites, especially in exhibiting excellent performance in impact resistance and energy absorption [2]. In this paper, AS4 graphite fiber reinforced polyether-ether-ketone (AS4/PEEK) composite was adopted to investigate the fabrication technology and mechanical properties of the three-dimensional sandwich structure with lattice core.

Fig. 1. Tail wing of G650 Aircraft

Fig. 2. TAPAS torsion box

Fabrication

Fig. 2. (a) The designed mould for fabricating AS4/PEEK lattice core; (b) Fabrication process of AS4/PEEK lattice core.

Fig. 3. Facesheet-core connection: (a) traditional adhesive method; (b) *in-situ* hot-pressing method.

Results

Fig. 4. Compression test results of specimens with different relative densities: (a) stress-strain curves; failure modes.

Fig. 5. Impact failure modes of specimens at different impact energy and position.

Conclusions

- A hot stamping process is proposed to fabricate AS4/PEEK lattice cores.
- An *in-situ* hot-pressing connection technology without additional connecting material is proposed to connect facesheets and lattice cores.
- The failure modes of AS4/PEEK lattice structure were observed under compression loading, including buckling, delamination and fracture of core struts.
- The impact damages of AS4/PEEK lattice structure were observed, which are affected by relative density of core, impact energy and impact position.
- The establishment and validation of FE model provide a way to investigate the designed lattice structures prior to conducting tests.

References

- [1] B. Xu, S. Yin, Y. Wang. Long-fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite lattice structures: Fabrication and compressive properties[J]. *Compos Part A-Appl S*, 2017, 97:41-50.
- [2] W. Tan, B. G. Falzon. Modelling the crush behaviour of thermoplastic composites [J]. *Compos Sci Technol*, 134:57-71, 2016.